

Measurement of Some Immunological Parameters, Hematologic Outcomes and Physiological Features for Graves' Disease in Babylon City, Iraq

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ABSTRACT

Graves' disease (GD) is an autoimmune disease that infected some people and describe as a disorder in the thyroid gland that leads to a hyperactive thyroid gland leading to the overproduction of thyroid hormones resulting from an attached immune system for the thyroid gland

The aims of this study were to Measurement of some immunological parameters (IL-2 & IgG), hematologic outcomes (routine CBC tests), and physiological features of Graves' disease in .Babylon City, Iraq

Study subjects (GD and Control Groups) & Demographic data: Study conducted from January 2022 to March 2022, samples for immunologic (IL-2, IgG & hematologic tests (routine CBC) were blood samples taken from both (n=94) Hospital-admitted patients with Graves' disease symptoms from Imam Al-Sadiq Teaching Hospital\ Thyroid gland diseases Center- First Floor and compare them with (60) represent healthy control, in both sexes, of different age groups ranging from (>38-<52 years)., in Babylon city. The researchers follow the Ethics committee of health & academic directorates. Data analysis using SPSS system to determine significant differences between data, p-value less than (<0.05) ANOVA. All values are expressed as the mean standard deviation (SD) **for sex, age groups, and test results in both GD & control groups.**

KEYWORDS: Graves' disease, IgG , IL-2 ,CBC test.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:

24 May 2023

Available on:

<https://ijpbms.com/>

INTRODUCTION

Graves' disease (GD) is named after Dr. Robert J. Graves who first described a case of it in 1835. The thyroid gland is an endocrinal gland that secretes a thyroxine hormones. Thyroid gland autoimmune disturbances are caused by the immune system attacking healthy tissues by creating antibodies, which provokes the thyroid to grow and produce more thyroid hormones than necessary for normal body functions. These antibodies are known as thyroid stimulating immunoglobulins (TSIs).

GD is responsible for 60-80% of clinical cases of hyperthyroidism and is one of the most prevalent autoimmune diseases [1]. Similar to other autoimmune diseases, GD is usually triggered by environmental factors in genetically predisposed individuals. The diagnosis of GD is made in the presence of a diffusely enlarged thyroid gland, thyrotoxicosis, and a possible involvement of the connective

tissues around the orbits and in the skin. So, disease suspected based on symptoms and findings during a physical examination, but to confirm the diagnosis, further blood or imaging tests should be carried out. These are used to conclusively diagnose GD and differentiate it from other autoimmune diseases that feature the presence of thyroid antibodies [2]. However, in regions without iodine deficiency, GD is the most common cause of hyperthyroidism, constitutes about 80% of hyperthyroidism cases, while hyperfunctioning autonomous adenomas are the most common cause in regions facing iodine deficiency. Thyroid function disorders are among the most common endocrine diseases. All body tissues need thyroid hormones for normal development, differentiation, metabolic balance, and physiological function. Hematological abnormalities have frequently been reported in thyroid disorders. Anemia is

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the most prevalent disorder being defined in 20-60% of the patients with hypothyroidism [3].

The aims of this study were to Measurement of some immunological parameters, hematologic outcomes and physiological features for Graves' disease in Babylon City, Iraq.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study subjects (GD and Control Groups) & Demographic data

We retrospectively picked up patients who had been diagnosed as having a disease who showed hyperthyroidism. So, we studied (n=94) patients with Graves' disease in both sexes, of different age groups ranging from (>38-<52 years) and compare them with (60) represent control sample.

The collection of samples occurs during the period from January 2022 to March 2022 from Imam Al-Sadiq Teaching Hospital\ Thyroid gland diseases Center- First Floor, in Babylon city. All patients infected with diffusely enlarged thyroid gland and elevated thyroid hormones levels According to the guideline for diagnosis of Graves' disease.

Ethical Issue

Ethics committee of College of Science at Al-Qasim Green University, and the corresponding ethical committee of Babylon health directorate also the Hospital Administration upon they gave us their permission and approval for the research study.

Blood sampling collection, store and processing:

By measuring antibodies type IgG and IL-2 levels in the serum after the blood has been collected and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 min and stored at -80°C until be used. The serum was collected in an Apandtroft tube and held at -20°C for an ELISA technique test.

Statistical Analysis of data:

Data analysis was performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) latest version 26 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) software for windows, using the descriptive and correlation test, to determine significant differences between data, p-value less than (<0.05) was considered as a minutest value for statistical significance level. ANOVA appropriate (differences between sexes), X² test, and students' Independent T test (to test differences

between means). The results were expressed as Count and Mean are used to convey qualitative data. All values are expressed as the mean standard deviation (SD) for sex, age groups and test results in both GD & control groups.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Study subjects (GD and Control Groups) & Demographic data, were retrospectively picked up patients who had been diagnosed as having a disease who showed hyperthyroidism. So, we studied (n=94) patients with Graves' disease in both sexes, of different age groups ranging from (>38-<52 years) and compare them with (60) represent control sample.

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Blood sampling collection, store and processing done by measuring antibodies type IgG and IL-2 levels in the serum after the blood has been collected and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 min and stored at -80°C until be used. The serum was collected in an Eppendorf tube and held at -20°C for an ELISA technique test.

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1- Results between & within groups of GD patients & control groups:

The results of statistical tests between & within groups of GD patients & control groups, where within groups be more significantly different than between groups, as shown in (Table 1).

Table 1. Results of statistical tests between & within groups of GD patients & control groups.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2307.293	5	461.459	26.118	0.000
Within Groups	3215.663	182	17.668		
Total	5522.957	187			

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2- Results of Age groups of both GD patients & control groups

The results of statistical tests of Age groups of both GD patients & control groups, were the age group 31-40 be more significantly different than younger & elder age groups, as shown in (Table 2), our results agree with the results of Pavlina M. Koseva *et al.* (2021), were GD typically affects people aged between 30 and 50, but it can develop at any age. There is a link between age and the symptoms and signs of hyperthyroidism [4].

Also in a study by Manji *et al.*, 880 patients were examined and grouped by age and sex. Many signs and symptoms showed little change with age until after the fifth decade of life when they began to decrease gradually. Thus, in patients 50 years old and above, the disease becomes more difficult to diagnose as there isn't enough information present, and the

significance of the existing data may not be appreciated. Hence, identification of the symptoms and signs specific to each age group is the key to improving the rates of early detection and successful treatment of hyperthyroidism [5]. Graves' disease (GD) is the most common cause of hyperthyroidism in children and adolescents. Pathogenesis of GD is complex and includes both genetic and environmental factors, such as cigarette smoking, high dietary iodine intake, stress and pregnancy. In children it may occur at any age with a peak during adolescence, and similarly to adults, it is much more frequent in girls than in boys. Age is an important factor in GD also determining the response to treatment, As GD tends to relapse more often in the young, it can be speculated that these individuals harbor a strong genetic susceptibility. This notion is supported by the finding that monozygotic twins share concordance for GD in roughly 75% of cases.

Table 2. Results of statistical tests of Age groups of both GD patients & control groups.

Age groups	Mean Difference	LSD	Sig.
21 - 30	6.692	3.346	0.000
31 - 40	7.431	3.348	0.000
41 - 50	6.643	3.321	0.000

3- Results of Immunological parameters (IL-2 & IgG) according GD patients & control groups in both sexes (male & female)

The results of statistical tests (M, SD & t-value) for Immunological parameters (IL-2 & IgG) according GD patients & control groups in both sexes (male & female), as shown in (Table 3).

Table 3. Results of statistical tests (M, SD & t-value) for Immunological parameters (IL-2 & IgG) according GD patients & control groups in both sexes (male & female).

	Graves' Patients				Table t-value	Healthy Control				Table t-value
	Male		Female			Male		Female		
	M	SD	M	SD		M	SD	M	SD	
IL-2	0.6277	0.43139	0.6483	0.43558	-0.213	7.6995	5.02144	7.2911	8.80367	0.264
IgG	15.2831	2.54698	15.3848	1.81845	-0.194	7.1682	3.42766	6.9978	3.43961	0.190

4- Results of Immunological parameters (IL-2 & IgG) according sex (male & female) of both GD patients & control groups:

The results of statistical tests (M, SD & t value) for Immunological parameters (IL-2 & IgG) according sex (male & female) of both GD patients & control groups, as shown in (Table 4).

Table 4. results of statistical tests (M, SD & t value) for Immunological parameters (IL-2 & IgG) according sex (male & female) of both GD patients & control groups.

	Male					Female				
	Graves' Patients		Healthy Control		Table t-value	Graves' Patients		Healthy Control		Table t-value
	M	SD	M	SD		M	SD	M	SD	
IL-2	0.6483	0.43558	7.2911	8.80367	-4.083	0.6125	0.41690	7.6203	5.03649	-11.093
IgG	15.3848	1.81845	6.9978	3.43961	10.940	15.2938	2.56564	7.2647	3.50879	15.229

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A- Results of IL-2:

It's obvious that high levels of IL-2 found in healthy persons than in patients' samples

Autoimmune thyroid diseases (AITD) is composed of two main clinical entities, Graves' disease (GD) and Hashimoto's disease (HD), and is characterized by infiltration of the thyroid by T cells and B cells and the production of antibodies specific for thyroid antigens. Among immune-related genes, human leukocyte antigen (HLA), cytotoxic T lymphocyte-associated factor 4 (CTLA-4), CD40, and protein tyrosine phosphatase-22(PTPN22) have been found to be associated with susceptibility to AITD. In particular, because the major histocompatibility

complex region is highly polymorphic and relevant to many immune response genes, HLA is the most prominent candidate genetic factor for several autoimmune diseases , including AITD [6].

Among genes associated with the immune response, human leukocyte antigen (HLA) genes have been found to be associated with autoimmune thyroid diseases (AITD), including GD. However, taking into account the relevance of the major histocompatibility complex (MHC) for immune responses and high polymorphism of HLA region, it seems to play a prominent role as a molecular background of GD [7]. The present study has demonstrated the actual associations between HLA haplotype and GD. The application of the NGS method to genotype both MCH I and II classes in large groups of patients and controls has clarified many discrepancies present in the previous results possibly due to a lack of allelic specificity and/or the size of the groups being too small. Although there has been extensive research on the etiology of GD in the last decades, it has not been possible to identify a single causative agent, likely reflecting the fine balance between anergy and autoimmunity challenging our immune system throughout life. Genetic influences have been extensively studied. Disappointingly, effect sizes of genetic predictors remain rather weak , with ORs of approximately 2, albeit with HLA-loci being the strongest [8].

B- Results of IgG

The most common cause of hyperthyroidism in iodine-sufficient areas is Graves' disease, and the cause of Graves' disease is thought to be multifactorial, arising from the loss of immunotolerance and the development of autoantibodies that stimulate thyroid follicular cells by binding to the TSH receptor [9, 10].

Thyroid disorders affect immunological parameters and these effects were found to be more prominent in the case of

hyperthyroidism in comparison with hypothyroidism. Serum autoantibodies against thyroid hormones can be a great marker to diagnose autoimmune thyroid diseases and can be used to measure the status of the diseases, the severity of the diseases, and response to treatment with antithyroid drugs [11, 12]. The level of various autoantibodies like thyroglobulin antibody (TG Ab), anti-thyroglobulin antibody (anti-TG Ab), thyroid peroxidase antibody (TPO Ab), and anti-thyroid peroxidase antibody (anti-TPO Ab) was found to be significantly higher in hyperthyroid patients than in the control group. A large number of hypothyroidism patients also had detectable concentrations of anti-TG and anti-TPO antibodies [13, 14].

According sexes (male & female):

Hyperthyroidism (Graves' disease) is an endocrine disorder with about 2% prevalence in females and 0.2% in males (1-3) and an estimated annual incidence rate of 20 per 100,000 population.

There is a clear sex difference in the prevalence of most autoimmune diseases. Females are generally more frequently affected than males, GD in particular being seven to eight times more common in women than in men [15, 16].

There are various mechanisms through which gender influences the predisposition to autoimmune diseases: differences in the body's immune response, organ vulnerability, sex hormones, reproductive capacity including pregnancy, parental inheritance, and epigenetics. For this reason, sex is considered an important factor in determining the mechanisms that influence the onset and development of an autoimmune disease [17, 18].

The global prevalence of GD has been reported to range from 0.5% to 2% of the population, with an incidence of 1 in 4000 persons per year [19]. Similar to other AIDs, GD is predominantly found in females- with a female-to-male ratio of (4 to 6)- and occurs predominantly in the third and fourth decade of life. Geographic variations in the incidence of GD may be due to genetic variations and/or exposure to local factors, but immigrants from lower risk regions acquire a similar risk over time as people in the new area of residence [20, 21].

Results of Hematologic outcomes (CBC tests) in GD patients & control groups:

The results of Hematologic outcomes (CBC tests) of both GD patients & control groups, where statistical analysis of (Mean & standard deviation, also t- test and significances are conducted, as shown in (Table 5).

Table 5. Results of Hematologic outcomes (CBC tests) of both GD patients & control groups.

CBC tests	Graves' Patients		Healthy Control		T-test	sig	statistical
	M	S.D.	M	S.D.			
WBC	12.17	4.94	6.40	1.33	8.91	0.00	Significant

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LYM	3.76	0.93	16.62	39.44	-3.17	0.00	Significant
MON	2.72	1.00	0.48	0.40	16.67	0.00	Significant
GRA	6.29	4.28	4.33	1.18	3.50	0.00	Significant
RBC	4.12	1.67	4.03	0.46	0.43	0.67	Random
HGB	8.81	2.03	14.87	1.41	-20.39	0.00	Significant
TLC	24.95	5.46	3184.51	9625.40	-3.19	0.00	Significant
MCV	86.43	8.34	9.25	1.08	71.82	0.00	Significant
MCH	30.04	3.26	28.41	2.46	3.34	0.00	Significant
MCHC	35.72	4.52	33.75	0.82	3.37	0.00	Significant
RDWS	35.75	4.52	37.57	5.06	-2.34	0.02	Significant
RDWC	14.82	5.90	13.22	1.61	2.06	0.04	Significant
PLT	284.56	136.84	272.44	113.98	0.57	0.57	Random
PCT	14.11	53.52	0.28	0.25	2.02	0.05	Significant
MPV	12.34	17.88	8.48	0.49	1.69	0.09	Random
PDWS	10.31	1.42	10.38	1.44	-0.30	0.76	Random
PDWC	36.65	7.21	38.32	1.38	-1.78	0.08	Random
P-LCC	59.83	23.20	69.05	22.01	-2.47	0.01	Significant
P-LCR	26.86	4.41	27.20	5.07	-0.45	0.66	Random

WBC= Total white cell count, **LYM**= Lymphocytes, **MON**= Monocytes, **GRA**= Granulocytes, **RBC**= Red blood cell count, **HGB**= Haemoglobin, **TLC**= Total Leukocyte Count, **MCV**= Mean cell volume, **MCH**= Mean cell haemoglobin, **MCHC**= Mean cell haemoglobin concentration, **RDW**= Red cell distribution width (S&C), **PLT**= Platelet count, **PCT**= , **MPV**= , **PDW** (S&C), **P-LCC** & **P-LCR**=

Hematological study of Graves' disease patients & control

The characteristics of the participants for the two groups are shown in Table 1. In two groups analysis (Group 1 and 2); lymphocyte ($p=0.047$), monocyte ($p=0.03$), platelet ($p=0.039$), free T3 ($p<0.001$), and free T4 ($p<0.001$) levels were significantly higher in Graves' disease group than in the control group. TSH ($p<0.001$) and NLR ($p=0.019$) were significantly lower in Graves' group than the control group. PLR was similar among the groups ($p>0.05$) [22].

Group 1a and Group 1b analysis demonstrated significant difference between groups in terms of monocyte ($p=0.013$), basophil ($p=0.002$), platelet ($p=0.029$) levels, NLR ($p=0.029$), freeT4 ($p<0.001$), free T3 ($p<0.001$) and TSH levels ($p<0.001$). Other parameters were similar between the groups [23].

Hyperthyroidism could result in changes in all blood cell lineages. Thyroid hormone excess due to increased tissue oxygen demands enhances erythropoiesis through hyperproliferation of immature erythroid progenitors and increased secretion of erythropoietin (EPO) by inducing erythropoietin gene expression [24]. Simultaneously, an increase in plasma volume, shorter erythrocyte life span, increases in iron turnover and iron, vitamin B12 or folate deficiency could result in anaemia. On the other hand, hyperthyroidism leads to a (usually mild) decrease in total white blood cell count, neutropenia and thrombocytopenia. Pancytopenia and autoimmune haemolytic anaemia are rare complications of thyroid hormone excess [25, 26].

From the above table it is clear that all the haematological indices are reduced in hypothyroid patients as compared to

hyperthyroid cases. However there is no significant difference in the MCV and MCH indicating that the cells are normocytic in both groups. RDW and AEC are also raised significantly within the hypothyroid group, though within the normal range.

In our study, WBC count was significantly higher in subacute thyroiditis than in Graves' disease. The percentage of neutrophil among WBC was significantly higher in subacute thyroiditis than in Graves' disease, and the percentages of lymphocyte and eosinophil in subacute thyroiditis were significantly

lower than those in Graves' disease. The guideline for diagnosis of subacute thyroiditis presented by the Japan Thyroid Association shows that patients often have preceding episodes of upper respiratory inflammation and high fever.

Further, a significant association between subacute thyroiditis and infection has been reported. Steroid levels increase immediately after stress such as infection in response to the stimulation of corticotropin-releasing hormone secretion by various cytokines [27, 28]. Hematological changes observed in subacute thyroiditis may be induced by excess steroid release due to increased inflammatory cytokines by infection [29].

Anemia may occur for several reasons, including abnormality of the formation and reduced half lifetime of RBCs or increased its osmotic [30].

There are contradictory evidences regarding hematological parameters in hyperthyroidism. Although early reports showed that Graves' disease is also associated with hematological disorders, anemia is not frequently observed in

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this group, and erythrocytosis is seen more common. Furthermore, hematological parameters mostly return to normal when euthyroid state achieved, although some other studies reported contradictory results [31].

Furthermore, the number of leucocytes may increase, remain normal, or may decline slightly when thyroid disorders present. A relative reduction in the neutrophils and increase in eosinophils and mononuclear cells may be observed in hyperthyroidism [32, 33].

Based on the previous studies, there are thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) receptors on myeloid and lymphoid cells, and these findings support the ability of TSH to influence the performance of lymphocytes [34, 35]. Regarding the high prevalence of thyroid disorders in Iran [36, 37, 38], this study was designed to measure the hematological changes in people with autoimmune hyperthyroidism before and after treatment in Gorgan city, Northeast of Iran.

DISCUSSION

Present results indicated mild anemia in about "40% of the studied population with Graves' disease, but no considerable reductions in the number of RBC count were observed in this study. There has been seen no significant disorders or changes in WBC count or platelet count before and after treatment. These results have been reported in other studies to some extent; some were in agreement with us and other revealed different results.

A significantly high prevalence of anemia (40% in females with thyroid disorders) has been reported in other studies associated with decreased number of RBCs, Hb concentration, packed cell volume (PCV), and mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH). Microcytic hypochromic and normocytic normochromic anemia were the most common detected types of anemia.

Anemia was the pioneer of hematologic disorders in other similar studies. In a study by Gianoukakis et al. on 87 newly diagnosed Graves' cases, anemia was reported in 33% of subjects. In 22% of all cases, anemia was exclusively related to thyroid dysfunction (41.6% of men compared to 17.5% of women). Antithyroid therapy for about 4 months resulted in normalization of Hb levels in 8 out of 9 cases (10.7 ± 0.8 g/dl to 13.5 ± 1.3 g/dl).

Regarding the statistically significant difference in RBC count, MCH, mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC), RBC distribution width (RDW), Hb, and HCT between hyperthyroid and hypothyroid cases, Dorgalaleh et al. suggested evaluating thyroid hormones in patients with unknown hematological dysfunctions.

Jafarzadeh et al. showed a significantly lower mean count of RBC and some RBC-related indices (HCT and Hb) in the hypothyroid group compared to the euthyroid group. Also, the mean MCV was significantly lower in hyperthyroid cases in comparison with the euthyroid group. This comparisons

was not available in our study, and we just enrolled Graves' cases with no control group.

the present study showed normal Hb levels in hyperthyroid cases. Very few reports have also documented the association of Pancytopenia with Grave's disease and the same has been shown to resolve dramatically after treatment of the latter. The pancytopenia in Grave's is postulated to be due to increased destruction or sequestration of the blood cells by an immune mediated mechanism. Studies have shown reduction in other haematological parameters like MCV, MCH, MCHC in hypothyroid states similar to our study, and have also proven that the same improves after the patient is started on Levothyroxine therapy. Conflicting studies have also shown no significant changes in MCV among hypo and hyper thyroid groups leaving a gap for a thorough understanding of the same.

As far as white blood cells are concerned, thyroid hormones play an important role in the regulation of human hematopoiesis as evident by previous studies.¹⁹ With regard to white blood cells, T3 has been shown to contribute towards normal production of B cells in the marrow by regulating the Pro B cell proliferation. The total leukocyte counts are also influenced by thyroid hormonal imbalances.

The lowest counts in our study were found in the hypothyroid group, the counts being significantly lower than the hyperthyroid group and not significantly lower when compared to the euthyroid groups. A study by Jafarzadeh et al. however showed no statistical variation in the leukocyte count between the three groups.

Platelet counts have also been assessed in thyroid disorders. Some studies have shown no significant change in platelet counts⁶, while few studies have shown low platelet counts in hypothyroid states. In our study the platelets though within the normal range were found to be significantly lower in the hypothyroid group compared to the hyper and euthyroid groups. An interesting study has shown the eosinophil count to be higher in hypothyroid group though not of statistical significance when compared with other groups. In the present study also the absolute eosinophil count was found to be the highest in the hypothyroid group, the same being statistically significant when compared to the hyperthyroid group. Serum IgE levels are also an indicator of the immunopathogenesis of allergic disorders reflected by absolute eosinophil counts in the peripheral blood. It has been shown that serum IgE levels are higher in hypo and hyperthyroid states suggesting a link between immune responses involving the cytokine releasing Th2 cells and thyroid hormones. To support the same it has been shown that the absolute number of pro- B, pre- B and B cells in the marrow of hypothyroid mice are significantly reduced. The same may be a subject for further detailed investigation and a subject of potential research in humans.

RDW- refers to the red cell distribution width, increase in which indicates RBCs of varying sizes. The study by Geetha and Srikrishna showed increased RDW in both hyper and

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hypothyroid subjects as compared to the euthyroid category, suggesting that the thyroid hormonal imbalance may influence the sizes of the RBCs. In our study the highest RDW was found in the hypothyroid group, similar to study by Montagnana et al. and Aktas et al. but was statistically not significant when compared to the hyper and euthyroid groups. Studies have also shown that in patients with increased RDW, but without iron deficiency, thyroid function must be evaluated together with folate and Vitamin B12 levels. Small sample size, unrevealed confounding factors present at the time of testing, associated undetected medical conditions if any are some of the limitations of the present study .

CONCLUSIONS

Thyroid disorders affect immunological parameters such as TG Ab, anti-TG Ab, TPO Ab, and anti-TPO Ab which can be used as markers for thyroid dysfunction. It has also been observed that thyroid diseases are associated with increased platelet activation which might increase the risk of atherothrombotic complications. A positive association of many inflammatory markers like CRP, PCT, ESR, and MPV levels has been established with thyroid dysfunction. Based on the literature reviewed in this article, it can be concluded that thyroid disorders play a significant role in the progression of diseases associated with multiple organs yet there is a need for more studies to establish the correlation between the type and severity of thyroidism and the organ affected.

Graves's disease is associated with various hematological abnormalities as shown from this study. There are serious changes in all the blood cell lineages. This shows that the bone marrow may be affected. Therefore the hematological alterations seen Grave disease patients could be attributable to autoimmunity, hyperthyroidism and nutritional deficiency . Genetic factors may be involved in this disorder. Infection and stress could also contribute to the complications in Gaves disease. Haematological parameters should be seriously monitored periodically in the course of treatment of Graves' disease over time.

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